

Method for assessing the impact of climate change on future energy production

Climate change in yield assessments

Why is it important?

Focus of presentation

Methodology, not results

Data collection at sites across the portfolio

Past measurements, future projections

Measurements

- 10-minute resolution
- Duration is campaign dependent.
- Near hub height.

Hindcast data

- 1-hour resolution
- 1990-present
- Near hub height.

Climate model projections

- 6-hourly resolution
- 1980-2100
- 100m, 150m, 200m

Wind farm information

- Power curves
- Hub heights
- Turbine locations
- Neighbouring wind farms

Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSP)

Different scenarios for the future

SSP	Radiative forcing [W/m ²]	CO ₂ emissions	Estimated warming (2081-2100) [°C]
SSP1	2.6	Net zero around 2075	1.8
SSP2	4.5	Falling from 2050	2.7
SSP3	7.0	Doubling by 2100	3.6
SSP5	8.5	Tripling by 2100	4.4

Bias-correcting climate data with on-site measurements

Predicting production impact with climate change variables

Harnessing our existing toolbox

Power curve

Wake model

Blockage effect

Predicting production impact with climate change variables

Processing power signals

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Concluding Remarks

Uncertainty much larger than impact

